

Teacher's management skills, well-being, religiosity, and academic motivation in Islamic education

Muhammad Thoyib¹, Subandi², Mispani², Aprezo Pardodi Maba³, Suhono⁴, Marlenatul Fitria³

¹Department of Islamic Education Management, Institut Agama Islam Negeri Ponorogo, Ponorogo, Indonesia

²Department of Islamic Education Management, Faculty of Tarbiyah, Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung, Lampung, Indonesia

³Department of Guidance and Counseling for Islamic Education, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, Universitas Ma'arif Lampung, Metro, Indonesia

⁴Department of English Education, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, Universitas Ma'arif Lampung, Metro, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Research on student academic motivation in Islamic educational institutions is currently in need of attention, as there are many schools based on Islam that have been overlooked by researchers. This research aims to investigate the role of perceived teacher management skills, psychological well-being, and religiosity towards students' academic motivation using data from Muslim participants. A cross-sectional design was used to achieve the research objectives. A total of 318 participants (Female=200, Male=118, age M=16.7, age SD=1.9) were voluntarily involved in this research. Participants were asked for their willingness to fill out five scales. The collected data was then analyzed using descriptive analysis and multiple linear regression after the required conditions were met. The results of the research indicate that academic motivation is well predicted by perceived teacher management skills and psychological well-being. These findings highlight the importance of teachers showing mastery of management skills, including skills in maintaining interpersonal relationships with students and parents, and designing programs that can foster the psychological well-being of students.

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Corresponding Author:

Aprezo Pardodi Maba

Department of Guidance and Counseling for Islamic Education, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, Universitas Ma'arif Lampung

Jalan RA. Kartini No. 28 Purwosari, Metro, Lampung, Indonesia

Email: aprezopm@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, many researchers have focused on addressing issues within the Islamic education institution. They consider that the studies to answer the problems that exist within Islamic education are as important as those in general education. This phenomenon is related to the awareness of researchers to place Islamic Education in its rightful position. Currently, there are interesting studies in the context of Islamic education such as Islamic education from a psychological, historical, social, cultural, and other perspectives. This can be a foothold in the development of Islamic education institutions in the future.

In this research, we focus on investigating perceived teacher management skills, psychological well-being, and religiosity towards students' academic motivation, which is conducted by involving participants from Islamic Education institutions. Perceived teacher management skills, psychological well-being, religiosity, students, and academic motivation are research variables that are often studied separately by other researchers. For example, some studies only investigate the relationship between the variables of psychological

well-being, religiosity, and academic motivation without involving the variable of perceived teacher management skills [1]–[4]. Therefore, in this study, we focus on examining the four variables together in order to contribute to the literature, specifically on academic motivation.

To date, literature addressing the issue of academic motivation in educational environments has been quite extensive. This can be seen from several literature reviews and meta-analyses on academic motivation. Not only that, researchers have also been quite responsive in conducting replication studies to confirm the accuracy of previous research. Furthermore, there is a study that addresses the issue of sustainability academic motivation [5]. Systematic reviews involving academic motivation variables include psychological interventions with virtual gamification [6], teaching methods [7], perceived autonomy support [8], and general studies within the field of psychology [9]. The aforementioned studies indicate that knowledge about academic motivation has been quite established.

Perceived teacher management skills refers to students' perceptions of the management skills possessed by teachers [10]. The skills in question are related to the structural awareness of the organization possessed by teachers and their role in improving relationships among members of the educational community [11]. Teacher management skills play an important role in maintaining a safe, comfortable, and peaceful school environment [12]. Thus, we can expect high achievement from students. With management skills, teachers can be the main reason in preventing aggressive behavior and bullying by students [11], [13], [14]. Additionally, teacher management skills are a good predictor of student achievement and motivation [15]–[17]. Therefore, students' perceptions of teacher management skills are important to consider, both in and out of the classroom.

Although psychological well-being tends to decrease among teenagers [18], some researchers have shown that psychological well-being is a good predictor of academic motivation [4], [19]. A person with good psychological well-being will show positive motivation and vice versa [20]. Although some students may experience good psychological well-being, others may experience difficult times with stress and anxiety, educational institutions with their programs will still strive to help students maintain their motivation [21], [22]. The dimension of academic motivation, intrinsic motivation, has a difference based on gender. Females show a negative correlation between psychological well-being and intrinsic motivation while males show the opposite indication [23].

In Islamic educational institutions, religiosity is very important as it indicates an individual's compliance with religious rules [24]–[28]. Based on this argument, we conceptualize religiosity as activities that are done to glorify oneself as someone who is obedient and regards God as an important or insignificant being. Therefore, it is not surprising that religiosity is indicated as one of the predictors for academic motivation [29], [30]. Further research is needed to confirm whether religiosity is a significant predictor of academic motivation, as the existing literature on this topic has only studied non-Muslim participants [29].

Based on the previous studies, we believe that perceived teacher management skills, psychological well-being, and religiosity have never been studied together in regards to their influence on academic motivation [1]–[3], [16], [19], [20]. This study contributes to the knowledge and literature on how the three variables play a role in academic motivation when studied together. The purpose of this research is to determine predictors of academic motivation among students. The findings of this study are expected to provide new insights for teachers and policymakers in formulating appropriate programs to enhance academic motivation among students. As a general, overarching hypothesis, it is hypothesized that teacher management skills, psychological well-being, and religiosity can predict students' academic motivation. In order to understand academic motivation among students, this study investigates several variables as predictors. These predictors are divided into three groups. First, teacher management skills. Second, psychological well-being. Lastly, religiosity. Emulating one study in existing literature, this current study did not present any direction of the prediction to prevent preconceived bias.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Design

The researchers used a quantitative, non-experimental, cross-sectional survey design for this research. Data was collected from participants through self-report, where participants were asked to rate themselves based on statements prepared by the researchers. The research design adopted in this study is cross-sectional survey, which is used to collect data at a single point in time. The purpose of this design is to examine the relationship between variables at a specific point in time.

2.2. Participants

The participants involved in this research are students from Islamic school in Lampung Province, Indonesia who were invited and given their consent to participate in the study on a convenience basis. This means that the participants filled out the research instrument voluntarily and without coercion. Data from 318

participants, who completed and met the requirements, will be analyzed to test the research hypotheses. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the research participants. The authors set the minimum number of required participants with ratio of 10:1, this indicating that at least 10 participants for one variable [31]. Therefore, the number of participants in this study met the minimum required sample size.

Table 1. Demographic information about the participants (N=318)

Variable		N
Gender	Male	118
	Female	200
Age		M=16.7 SD=1.9
Smoking	Yes	37
	No	281
Drinking alcohol in last 30 days	Yes	15
	No	303

2.3. Instruments

There are five instruments used in this research, namely demographic questions, perceptions of teacher management skills, psychological well-being, religiosity, and a short version of academic motivation. In addition to demographic questions, the other four instruments mentioned previously are adaptations of English instruments. In general, the authors adapted these instruments using the following stages by Hernández; i) transliteration into Indonesian, ii) back-transliteration into English, iii) evaluation of transliteration accuracy, and iv) validation testing. The following is a list of the instruments used, including demographic questions [32].

2.3.1. Demographic questions

In order to contextualize the research, the authors collected some data on the characteristics of the participants. The characteristics information includes gender, age, religion, smoking habits, and whether they have consumed alcohol in the last 30 days. Those demographic questions will be used to identify the participant characteristics.

2.3.2. Perceived teacher management skills

The 11-item scale is adapted from the school-wide climate scale [10]. The scale aims to measure students' perceptions of their teachers' management skills. Examples of the statements include "Teachers and students have a good relationship", "Students' families are involved in school activities", and "Teachers set a good example of being approachable." The scale uses a 0 to 4 rating system, where a higher score indicates a better perception of teachers' management skills. The Cronbach's alpha for this instrument is at a good level.

2.3.3. Psychological well-being

In this research, the author used a shortened version (eight items) of the Brief Adolescent Psychological Well-being in School Scale [33] that was adapted to the Indonesian language [34]. This shortened version was created to prevent participants from changing their behavior when filling out the questionnaire, from being honest to dishonest and fabricated. This behavior usually occurs because the questionnaire is too long and tedious. The following are three examples of statements used in this shortened version: "At school, how often do I feel happy", "I get along well with my classmates", and "My school has good rules and facilities." The Cronbach's alpha of this instrument is .7, which was considered good, indicating that the scale has acceptable internal consistency.

2.3.4. Religiosity

In this research, two statements were used to measure religiosity, namely "Frequency of prayer/praying/worship" with answer options ranging from 1 (never) to 8 (several times a day) and "The role of God in daily life" with answer options ranging from 1 (not important at all) to 10 (very important). The higher the score shown by the participants indicates the higher religiosity. This instrument is adapted from the religiosity scale [24].

2.3.5. Short version of academic motivation

The initial version of the academic motivation scale was developed by Vallerand [35], [36]. This initial version was then adapted to Indonesian [36] and in the same year, Natalya [37] created a short version of the Academic Motivation Scale. The following are three example statements used in this short version:

“I really enjoy the classes/materials during school”, “I feel that this school is useful for the career I want”, and “Because for me, school is fun.” The Cronbach’s alpha of this instrument is .9.

2.4. Procedures

After obtaining approval from Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung and Universitas Ma’arif Lampung with Decision Letter No. 11/0239/IAIMNU/LPM/III/2022 regarding research permission, the author began designing the research activities that will be carried out. First, the author prepared the instruments that will be used and administered them into a Google Form. Second, the Google Form distributed to the potential participants. Before the potential participants filled out the form, they were given explanations about the purpose of data collection, confidentiality statement, and were asked for their voluntary participation. The author also prepared door prizes for selected participants. Third, after sufficient data from the participants was collected, the author began the data analysis.

2.5. Data analysis

The data were analyzed with SPSS 24. Descriptive analysis was conducted to present characteristics of the sample population, specifically sociodemographic factors, fear, and anxiety. Furthermore, two criteria were used in the assumption test for doing linear regression analysis. Firstly, the residual value or error should be normally distributed ($p > .05$). Secondly, there is no multi collinearity by looking at VIF value being < 10 [38]. The residual value is normally distributed based ($p = .226 > .05$) on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and all VIF values are < 10 . The results of the assumption test showed that all assumptions are met. Thus, regression analysis can be done. The previously stated hypothesis for this present study was then tested using multiple linear regression analysis and mediation analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

Table 1 illustrates the demographic information of the participants. The information in Table 1 includes i) more female participants than male participants; ii) the average age of participants is 16.7 years with a standard deviation of 1.9 years; iii) the majority of participants do not smoke and do not consume alcohol. This information is necessary in research results generalization.

Based on Table 2, all variables are positively correlated with each other. The relationship between the variable of psychological well-being and academic motivation is indicated to have the strongest positive correlation ($r = .596, p < .01$). Then, it followed by a positive correlation between the variable of perceived teacher management skills and psychological well-being ($r = .537, p < .01$). Furthermore, a positive correlation is also found between the variables of teacher management skills and academic motivation ($r = .439, p < .01$), and teacher management skills and religiosity ($r = .195, p < .01$).

Table 2. Descriptive and correlation analysis (N=318)

Variables	M	SD	2	3	4
1. Perceived teacher management skills	37.44	7.63	.537**	.195**	.439**
2. Psychological well-being	33.24	4.25		.056	.596**
3. Religiosity	17.19	1.88			.086
4. Academic motivation	37.81	4.31			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results of the regression test can be seen in Table 3. The proposed model ($F(3) = 63.114, p < .05, R^2 = .376$) predicts 37.6% of academic motivation. The variables that significantly predict academic motivation are perceived teacher management skills ($\beta = .161, p = .003$) and psychological well-being ($\beta = .505, p = .000$). Meanwhile, religiosity was not found to be a significant predictor of academic motivation ($\beta = .026, p = .574$).

Based on the mediation analysis conducted using Hayes’ method [39] as shown in Table 2, perceived teacher management skills showed that it explains 28.87% of the variance in psychological well-being ($R^2 = .2887$) ($\beta = .299, t = 11.3251, p = .000$), indicating that perceived teacher management skills has a positive impact on psychological well-being. The relationship between perceived teacher management skills and psychological well-being explains 37.57% of the variance in academic motivation ($R^2 = .3757$) (perceived teacher management skills $\beta = .094, t = 3.1681, p = .001$ and psychological well-being $\beta = .513, t = 9.5969, p = .000$). These results indicate that the model of perceived teacher management skills and psychological well-being is able to predict academic motivation simultaneously. The bootstrapping results showed that the indirect effect estimation with 95% confidence interval is .0996 - .2173 ($\beta = .254$). This estimation indicates that if perceived

teacher management skills value is good, LLCI and ULCI both have positive values and there is no value of 0. This proves that perceived teacher management skills have a significant impact on academic motivation through psychological well-being as a mediator variable.

Table 3. The multiple linear regression test with academic motivation as the dependent variable (N=318)

Variables	B	SE	β	t	p
Perceived teacher management skills	.091	.030	.161	2.994	.003
Psychological well-being	.516	.054	.508	9.603	.000
Religiosity	.059	.104	.026	.563	.574
Academic motivation as DV	df	F	R ²	Adj. R ²	p
	3	63.114	.376	.370	.000

Table 4. The effect of psychological well-being as mediator in the relationship of perceived teacher management skills and academic motivation

Variables	β	t	p	SE	LLCI	ULCI	R	R ²	F	p
PWB as DV							.5373	.2887	128.2572	.000
PTMS	.299	11.3251	.000	.0265	.2476	.3518				
AM as DV							.6129	.3757	11.7153	.000
PTMS	.094	3.1681	.001	.0299	.0359	.1534				
PWB	.513	9.5969	.000	.0535	.4085	.6193				
Total effect	.248	8.6962	.000	.0286	.1924	.3049				
Indirect effect	.154			.0301	.0996	.2173				

Note: PWB = psychological well-being; PTMS = perceived teacher management skills; AMS = academic motivation

3.2. Discussion

The purpose of this research is to determine the predictors of academic motivation in students. This research objective has been achieved. Through several stages of analysis, the three predictor groups (perceptions of teacher management skills, psychological well-being, and religiosity) proposed in this research were able to predict academic motivation by 37.6%. In the mediation analysis, psychological well-being was found to be a significant mediator in the relationship between perceived teacher management skills and academic motivation.

The three predictor groups (perceptions of teacher management skills, psychological well-being, and religiosity) proposed in this research have been proven to be able to predict academic motivation. This finding has been predicted by the author, as stated in the hypothesis. Thus, the results obtained in this research support previous research findings [16], [17]. It should be noted that these findings were obtained from research conducted in general institutions, not institutions based on religiosity or in this case, Islamic education institutions. This finding suggests – although further investigation is needed – that there is no difference between general institutions and religious institutions.

Based on the argument presented in the introduction, previous studies have primarily been conducted in general institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to reconfirm the effect of religiosity on academic motivation. The results of this study have shown that there is no difference in the effect of religiosity on academic motivation, whether in general institutions or institutions based on religion [29], [30], [40]. This means that religiosity may be considered equally important in both general institutions and institutions based on Islam, even though religiosity in Islamic educational institutions is particularly important as it indicates compliance with religious rules [24], [26]–[28]. However, in the context of academic motivation, religiosity may be considered equally important in both general institutions and institutions based on Islam.

In the mediation analysis, psychological well-being was found to be a significant mediator in the relationship between perceived teacher management skills and academic motivation. Previous studies have confirmed that psychological well-being is a predictor for academic motivation [4], [19], [41]. However, there has not been specific research investigating the relationship between psychological well-being and perceived teacher management skills in relation to academic motivation. Nonetheless, the theory of classroom climate can serve as a reference for interpreting the findings of this study.

Classroom climate is a construct that describes the combination and accumulation of various learning experiences that students encounter [42]. Classroom climate plays an important role in the development of students' academic, behavioral, and socio-emotional aspects. In this context, perceived teacher management skills are one of the indicators of classroom climate [43]. Therefore, this research finding is consistent with previous researches [44]–[46], in suggesting that psychological well-being plays a role in predicting the relationship between perceived teacher management skills and academic motivation.

3.3. Implications

The results of this study indicate that perceived teacher management skills, psychological well-being, and religiosity can simultaneously affect academic motivation. The study also shows that, within the broader framework of classroom climate, the relationship between perceived teacher management skills and academic motivation can be mediated by psychological well-being. These findings should be taken into consideration by policy makers in the field of education to improve the image of teacher management, psychological well-being, and religiosity in order to enhance students' academic motivation without compartmentalizing or separating these variables.

3.4. Limitations and future directions

The research instruments used are adaptations of instruments in foreign languages. The authors would like to point out that these instruments may have bias when the study focuses on participants who have a strong belief in religion, such as Muslim participants [24], [26]–[28]. To anticipate this possibility, future research should focus on developing instruments that are specifically designed to measure these variables among Muslim participants. Furthermore, to improve the generalization, detailed participants demographical data need to be considered for future study.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis conducted, it can be concluded that perceived teacher management skills and psychological well-being are significant factors in predicting academic motivation of students. Therefore, teachers should pay attention to how they can improve their management image; for example, clearly define the roles and responsibilities, encourage professional development, and encourage regular communication or collaboration. Furthermore, it is also important to develop programs that can enhance the psychological well-being of students to increase academic motivation. On the other hand, religiosity was not proven to be a significant factor in predicting academic motivation.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bożek, P. F. Nowak, and M. Blukacz, "The relationship between spirituality, health-related behavior, and psychological well-being," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 11, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01997.
- [2] S. Fatima, S. Sharif, and I. Khalid, "How does religiosity enhance psychological well-being? Roles of self-efficacy and perceived social support.," *Psychology of Religion and Spirituality*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 119–127, May 2018, doi: 10.1037/rel0000168.
- [3] C. Ganaprakasam and F. D. Hutagalung, "Religion on Psychological Well-Being and Self-Efficacy among Secondary School Students," *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, vol. 8, no. 5, May 2018.
- [4] S. Ozer and S. J. Schwartz, "Academic motivation, life exploration, and psychological well-being among emerging adults in Denmark," *Nordic Psychology*, vol. 72, no. 3, pp. 199–221, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1080/19012276.2019.1675088.
- [5] M. Blašková, J. Majchrzak-Lepczyk, D. Hrníková, and R. Blaško, "Sustainable Academic Motivation," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 21, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11215934.
- [6] J. Xu *et al.*, "Psychological interventions of virtual gamification within academic intrinsic motivation: A systematic review," *Journal of Affective Disorders*, vol. 293, pp. 444–465, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2021.06.070.
- [7] M. Saeedi, R. Ghafouri, F. J. Tehrani, and Z. Abedini, "The effects of teaching methods on academic motivation in nursing students: A systematic review," *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, vol. 10, no. 271, 2021.
- [8] R. Okada, "Effects of perceived autonomy support on academic achievement and motivation among higher education students: A meta-analysis," *Japanese Psychological Research*, vol. 65, no. 3, pp. 230–242, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1111/jpr.12380.
- [9] L. Nguyen Phuc and T. Tran Thi Le, "Learners' academic motivation in psychology: a systematic review," *Journal of Science Educational Science*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 75–84, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.18173/2354-1075.2020-0112.
- [10] P. E. Muñoz, J. A. Casas, R. Del Rey, R. Ortega-Ruiz, G. Cerda, and C. Pérez, "Validation and cross-cultural robustness of the school-wide climate scale (SCS) across Spanish and Chilean students," *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, vol. 56, pp. 182–188, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.stueduc.2018.01.002.
- [11] J. A. Casas, R. Ortega-Ruiz, and R. Del Rey, "Bullying: The impact of teacher management and trait emotional intelligence," *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, vol. 85, no. 3, pp. 407–423, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1111/bjep.12082.
- [12] J. Duong and C. P. Bradshaw, "Using the extended parallel process model to examine teachers' likelihood of intervening in bullying," *Journal of School Health*, vol. 83, no. 6, pp. 422–429, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1111/josh.12046.
- [13] R. Uz and M. Bayraktar, "Bullying toward teachers and classroom management skills," *European Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 647–657, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.12973/eu-jer.8.2.647.
- [14] S. Susanto, "Child mentoring to cultivate resilience of vulnerability to bullying," *Bulletin of Community Engagement*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 36–44, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.51278/bce.v3i1.448.
- [15] N. İhtiyaroğlu, "Analysis of the predictive role of teachers' effective communication skills and motivation levels on classroom management profiles," *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 17–25, 2019.
- [16] Z. Sahito and P. Vaisanen, "Effect of time management on the job satisfaction and motivation of teacher educators: A narrative analysis," *International Journal of Higher Education*, vol. 6, no. 2, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.5430/ijhe.v6n2p213.
- [17] W. van Dijk, N. A. Gage, and N. Grasley-Boy, "The relation between classroom management and mathematics achievement: A multilevel structural equation model," *Psychology in the Schools*, vol. 56, no. 7, pp. 1173–1186, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1002/pits.22254.
- [18] C. S. Conley, A. C. Kirsch, D. A. Dickson, and F. B. Bryant, "Negotiating the transition to college," *Emerging Adulthood*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 195–210, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.1177/2167696814521808.

- [19] A. J. Martin, B. Papworth, P. Ginns, and G. A. D. Liem, "Boarding school, academic motivation and engagement, and psychological well-being," *American Educational Research Journal*, vol. 51, no. 5, pp. 1007–1049, Oct. 2014, doi: 10.3102/0002831214532164.
- [20] L. Emadpoor, M. G. Lavasani, and S. M. Shahcheraghi, "Relationship between perceived social support and psychological well-being among students based on mediating role of academic motivation," *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 284–290, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s11469-015-9608-4.
- [21] S. J. Schwartz, "Turning point for a turning point," *Emerging Adulthood*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 307–317, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1177/2167696815624640.
- [22] B. Bukhori, S. Ma'arif, S. A. binti Panatik, I. B. Siaputra, and A. A. Al Afghani, "Study on Muslim University students in Indonesia: The mediating role of resilience in the effects of Religiosity, social support, self-efficacy on subjective well-being," *Islamic Guidance and Counseling Journal*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 152–171, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.25217/igcj.v5i2.2972.
- [23] Á. L. González Olivares, Ó. Navarro, F. J. Sánchez-Verdejo, and A. Muelas, "Psychological well-being and intrinsic motivation: relationship in students who begin University studies at the school of education in Ciudad Real," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 11, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.02054.
- [24] N. A. Aminuddin and H. S. Abd. Hamid, "Predictors of deviant behavior justification among Muslims: sociodemographic factors, subjective well-being, and perceived religiousness," *Islamic Guidance and Counseling Journal*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 144–157, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.25217/igcj.v4i2.1814.
- [25] N. Daulay *et al.*, "Religiosity as moderator of stress and well-being among Muslim students during the pandemic in Indonesia," *Islamic Guidance and Counseling Journal*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 88–103, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.25217/igcj.v5i2.2696.
- [26] A. Begum, L. Jingwei, M. Haider, M. M. Ajmal, S. Khan, and H. Han, "Impact of environmental moral education on pro-environmental behaviour: Do psychological empowerment and Islamic religiosity matter?" *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 4, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph18041604.
- [27] F. Osella and B. Soares, "Religiosity and its others: lived Islam in West Africa and South India," *Social Anthropology*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 466–481, May 2020, doi: 10.1111/1469-8676.12767.
- [28] R. R. Diana, M. Chirzin, K. Bashori, F. M. Suud, and N. Z. Khairunnisa, "Parental engagement on children character education: The influences of positive parenting and agreeableness mediated by religiosity," *Jurnal Cakrawala Pendidikan*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 428–444, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.21831/cp.v40i2.39477.
- [29] S. T. Butler-Barnes, T. T. Williams, and T. M. Chavous, "Racial pride and religiosity among African American boys: Implications for academic motivation and achievement," *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 486–498, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1007/s10964-011-9675-1.
- [30] S. Fatima, M. Mehfooz, and S. Sharif, "Role of Islamic religiosity in predicting academic motivation of university students," *Psychology of Religion and Spirituality*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 377–386, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1037/re10000097.
- [31] J. F. Hair, G. T. M. Hult, C. M. Ringle, M. Sarstedt, N. P. Danks, and S. Ray, *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-80519-7.
- [32] A. Hernández, M. D. Hidalgo, R. K. Hambleton, and J. Gómez-Benito, "International test commission guidelines for test adaptation: A criterion checklist," *Psicothema*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 390–398, 2020.
- [33] L. Tian, D. Wang, and E. S. Huebner, "Development and validation of the brief adolescents' subjective well-being in school scale (BASWBSS)," *Social Indicators Research*, vol. 120, no. 2, pp. 615–634, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s11205-014-0603-0.
- [34] W. Prasetyawati, T. Rifameutia, R. Gillies, and P. Newcombe, "The adaptation of a brief adolescent subjective well-being in school scale (BASWBSS), the student subjective well-being scale in the Indonesian context," *ANIMA Indonesian Psychological Journal*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 184–203, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.24123/aipj.v36i2.2277.
- [35] R. J. Vallerand, L. G. Pelletier, M. R. Blais, N. M. Briere, C. Senecal, and E. F. Vallieres, "The academic motivation scale: A measure of intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation in education," *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 1003–1017, Dec. 1992, doi: 10.1177/0013164492052004025.
- [36] L. Natalya and C. V. Purwanto, "Exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis of the academic motivation scale (AMS)–Bahasa Indonesia," *Makara Human Behavior Studies in Asia*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 29–42, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.7454/hubs.asia.2130118.
- [37] L. Natalya, "Validation of academic motivation scale: Short Indonesian language version," *ANIMA Indonesian Psychological Journal*, vol. 34, no. 1, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.24123/aipj.v34i1.2025.
- [38] A. Alin, "Multicollinearity," *WIREs Computational Statistics*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 370–374, 2010, doi: 10.1002/wics.84.
- [39] A. F. Hayes, "Partial, conditional, and moderated mediation: Quantification, inference, and interpretation," *Communication Monographs*, vol. 85, no. 1, pp. 4–40, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1080/03637751.2017.1352100.
- [40] M. A. Fauzi, S. Suroso, and M. Farid, "Relationship between religiosity and self-control with cybersex behavior in school students," *Psychomachina*, vol. 1, no. 1–8, 2023.
- [41] K. Pang, P. Liu, S. Li, L. Zou, M. Lu, and L. Martínez, "Concept lattice simplification with fuzzy linguistic information based on three-way clustering," *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, vol. 154, pp. 149–175, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijar.2022.12.009.
- [42] R. L. Chapman, L. Buckley, M. Sheehan, and I. Shochet, "School-based programs for increasing connectedness and reducing risk behavior: A systematic review," *Educational Psychology Review*, vol. 25, no. 1, p. 95, 2013, doi: 10.1007/s10648-013-9216-4.
- [43] G. Djigic and S. Stojiljkovic, "Classroom management styles, classroom climate and school achievement," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 29, pp. 819–828, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.310.
- [44] S. Mulyani *et al.*, "emotional regulation as a remedy for teacher burnout in special schools: Evaluating school climate, teacher's work-life balance and children behavior," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 12, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.655850.
- [45] F. Soheili, H. Alizadeh, J. M. Murphy, H. S. Bajestani, and E. D. Ferguson, "Teachers as leaders: The Impact of Adler-Dreikurs Classroom Management Techniques on Students' Perceptions of the Classroom environment and on academic achievement," *The Journal of Individual Psychology*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 440–461, 2015, doi: 10.1353/jip.2015.0037.
- [46] M.-T. Wang, J. L. Degol, J. Amemiya, A. Parr, and J. Guo, "Classroom climate and children's academic and psychological wellbeing: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Developmental Review*, vol. 57, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.dr.2020.100912.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Muhammad Thoyib completed his elementary and junior high school education in Bangil Pasuruan, Indonesia before receiving a scholarship to pursue his studies in various educational institutions throughout Indonesia. He has specialized in Islamic education and educational management and received scholarships for his Master's and Doctorate degrees. He can be contacted at email: thoyib@iainponorogo.ac.id.

Subandi is a Professor in Islamic Education Management at the Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung. Currently, he occupied Vice Dean for Student Affairs and Cooperation position at Faculty of Tarbiya and Teacher Training Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung. He can be contacted at email: subandi@radenintan.ac.id.

Mispani is Rector and associate professor for Islamic Education at the Universitas Ma'arif Lampung. His research interests are Islamic Education and Educational management. He can be contacted at email: mispani@umala.ac.id.

Aprezo Pardodi Maba is a lecturer and researcher at Universitas Ma'arif Lampung. His research interests are educational psychology, guidance and counseling, religiosity in psychology, help-seeking, and mental health literacy. He can be contacted at email: aprezopm@gmail.com.

Suhono is a lecturer at English Education Departement at Universitas Ma'arif Lampung. He is passionate on linguistics research and has published several papers related to this field. He can be contacted at email: suhono120708@gmail.com.

Marlenatul Fitria is a student of Guidance and Counseling for Islamic Education Universitas Ma'arif Lampung, Indonesia. She can be contacted at email: marlenatulfitria97@gmail.com.